

PHARMACEUTICAL COMPANIES IN THE DIGITAL AGE: TOP MANAGEMENT'S ATTITUDE TO CORPORATE COMMUNICATIONS

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Relevance: The authors of the article consider the problem of improving internal and external communications in the context of digital transformation. This fact requires the top management of pharmaceutical companies to rethink their approaches and move to more effective corporate communication models.

The aim of the study is to analyze the attitude of top management of pharmaceutical companies to digital communications.

Materials and methods: the methodological basis of the research is the works of scientists in the field of digitalization E. V. Karonsky, S. M. Golovko, approaches to the study of corporate culture L. L. Konstantin, D. Denisov, E. V. Levkin, S. A. Lipatov, R. K. Nesmeyanova. Research methods: system analysis, content analysis, sociological survey-questionnaire.

Results: A questionnaire consisting of 27 multiple-choice questions was developed. The survey involved 20 representatives of the top management of manufacturing and distribution pharmaceutical companies. Data analysis showed that the majority of respondents (65%) rate the level of interaction between departments as satisfactory. Only 45% of respondents associate the improvement of corporate culture with the growth of operational efficiency through digital tools. Exactly half - 50% of the study participants consider the introduction of digital document management systems to be a priority, which is consistent with industry-wide trends. The results of the study demonstrate that successful transformation of internal and external communications requires a comprehensive approach, including document flow automation (50%), productivity improvement (45%) and optimization of information exchange (45%). The overwhelming majority of managers (90%) recognize the positive impact of transparency of business processes on the efficiency of companies. The revealed quarter of companies with a low level of process transparency and 15% of organizations with unsatisfactory inter-structural interaction indicate the need for systemic changes in approaches to managing and organizing corporate communications. The current problem, which is indicated by the results of the study, is a formal approach to digitalization, when the introduction of tools is not supported by a change in corporate culture and management approaches.

Conclusions: despite the proclaimed willingness to open up business processes, only half of the companies understand the need for a systemic transformation of management models and associate this with improving corporate communications and increasing operational efficiency. The revealed gap between the declared value of transparency and real strategic priorities indicates the continuing formal approach to digitalization, in which the introduction of tools outstrips the change in corporate culture. This creates risks of low returns on investments in digital solutions and is a key barrier to full-fledged digital transformation in the pharmaceutical industry. The results obtained contribute to understanding the factors of readiness of top management of pharmaceutical companies for digital transformation and can serve as a basis for developing more effective strategies for implementing digital communication solutions in the industry.